

Physical Parameters of Aged Camel Meat Tenderized with Water Extract of Ginger Powder

Basim F. S. Al-Sanger

*Animal Production Department, Agriculture College,
Al-Muthanna University, Al-Muthanna, Iraq*

Abstract

From December 25, 2024, to January 22, 2025, the current study was carried out in the Poultry Laboratory at Al-Muthanna University's College of Agriculture. The purpose of the study was to ascertain how an aqueous extract of ginger powder affected some physiological characteristics of the aged camels' flesh. Fifteen samples of old camel meat were used in the study, brought from a slaughterhouse in Al-Muthanna Governorate. The current study used aged camel thigh meat, which was divided into five treatments, as follows: T1: (Negative control treatment) Samples were immersed in distilled water, T2: (Positive control treatment) Samples were immersed in 0.10% vinegar. T3, T4 and T5 Samples were immersed in a solution containing 0.15, 0.20 and 0.25% aqueous extract of ginger powder. The results of our study indicate that all the softening treatments with aqueous extract of ginger powder led to a significant increase in water holding capacity, and a significant decrease was observed in each of cooking loss, drip loss and thawing loss for all studied cuts of camel meat, namely thigh, shoulder and back, related to the two control actions, and the best treatments in which the results were obtained were Samples were immersed in a solution containing 0.20% aqueous extract of ginger powder (T4).

Keywords: *Physical parameters, aged camel meat, tenderized, water extract, ginger.*

Suggested citation: Al-Sanger, B.F.S. (2025). Physical Parameters of Aged Camel Meat Tenderized with Water Extract of Ginger Powder. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(6), 69-75. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(6).08

Introduction

Camel meat is one of the toughest meats due to its high connective tissue content compared to beef and sheep. Camels are resilient animals that have adapted to withstand harsh conditions and high temperatures, especially in extremely hot arid, semi-arid, and desert regions. This reduces the costs of raising and preparing meat (Ibrahim et al., 2025).

Camel meat is highly sought after in certain regions and countries, as Arabian camels are a good source of meat, especially in arid and semi-arid regions. This negatively impacts the meat of other animals due to camels' physiological characteristics, including their ability to withstand high temperatures and limited feed. Camel meat is a good source of animal protein, comparable in quality to beef and sheep, especially if the camels are young and less than three years old (Baba et al., 2021; Al Salman and Al-Gharawi, 2019).

Camel meat has become increasingly popular in recent years as an alternative meal with various distinctive properties, including high protein content, low fat and polyunsaturated fatty acids, as well as favorable meat quality attributes (Sulliman et al., 2020).

One of the most important physical characteristics of camel meat is its leaching fluid, which is the fluid lost when frozen meat is thawed. Increasing its percentage will reduce the nutritional value of the meat. This is because this fluid contains some important and essential nutrients in the composition of meat, particularly essential elements, minerals, vitamins, and salts (El-Badawi et al., 2024).

Si et al. (2022) showed, when studying the mineral content of camel and cow meat, that the liquid that oozes out when frozen meat is thawed contains 4.4% protein, in addition to containing large amounts of vitamins, especially water-soluble vitamins, B-complex vitamins, thiamine B1, riboflavin B2, niacin, and some mineral elements such as iron, copper, calcium, potassium, and zinc.

Eddie et al. (2017) indicated, when studying the physical characteristics and features of camel meat of different age groups, that the percentage of leaching fluid is affected by many factors, the most important of which is temperature, as exposing meat to high temperatures of up to 40-41 °C will lead to a significant increase in the leaching fluid of the meat. Another factor is the duration of freezing and storage, as increasing the duration of freezing will increase the leaching fluid.

Water holding capacity is an important sensory characteristic that affects the quality of meat. Water represents about 65-80% of the muscle composition, and most of this water is bound to muscle proteins. More than 90% of the water in muscle proteins is found inside the cells, especially between actin and myosin filaments (Barbut, 2024).

Tabite et al. (2019) found that more than 4-12% of the water in the muscles is located between the muscle fibers and that the water-holding capacity has a direct effect on the shrinkage of meat during storage due to the high loss of moisture. Therefore, the lost moisture containing soluble proteins is called “weep”, which causes a reduction in the value of the meat during the marketing process. Water in meat is in several forms, either bound to protein (water binding potential) at a rate of 4-5% and not separable from the meat, stable water (expressible moisture), which is the water removed from the meat when exposed to any external pressure, and free water (free drip), which is the water lost without any external pressure.

Abdelhadi et al. (2019) indicated that the water-holding capacity is affected by several factors, including the acidity (PH), which when low causes the protein to denature, causing a decrease in the number of reactive or active groups that bind the protein to the muscle and are necessary to bind water, causing a change in the protein structure and reducing the protein solubility. The reason for the decrease in the number of reactive groups is that the pH reaches the electrical equivalence point of muscle proteins, i.e. the number of positive and negative charges is equal, which leads to the tendency of these groups to attract each other, leaving only a few excess charges to interact with water.

Meat is greatly affected by cooking temperature, which causes several changes, the most important of which is the change in the composition and structure of meat proteins. The cooking process often does not lead to tenderizing meat, as there are two basic factors in the cooking process: cooking temperature and cooking duration, which greatly affect the texture of meat and thus affect the percentage of loss during the cooking process (Vashishth et al., 2021).

This study targets to determine the physical parameters the thigh meat of old camels tenderized with different planes of aqueous extract of ginger powder.

Materials and Methods

The current study was showed in the Al-Muthanna University's College of Agriculture's Poultry Laboratory, December 25, 2024–January 22, 2025. The study aimed to determine the result of an aqueous extract of ginger powder on some physiological parameters of the meat of old camels. Fifteen samples of old camel meat were used in the study, brought from a slaughterhouse in Al-Muthanna Governorate. Physical parameters tests of camel meat were conducted in the poultry laboratory in the Animal

Production Department, College of Agriculture, Al-Muthanna University. The meat of old male camels aged (8-10) years was used. The ages were determined through pre-slaughter examination by specialists in the model slaughterhouse and through the teething method (Younis *et al.*, 2025). Samples of old camel meat were taken from local slaughterhouses in Al-Muthanna Governorate, Samawah District. Small samples of 100 gm each were taken from the thigh, shoulder, and back, were placed in sealed polyethylene bags. Some of them were placed in the refrigerator for (24 hours) at (°5 C) for the purpose of cooling and preservation, while the other samples were kept in the freezer at (-°18 C) for the purpose of freezing and preservation until the start of the physical tests. The current study used aged camel thigh meat, which was divided into five treatments, as follows:

T1: Negative control.

T2: Positive control, were immersed in 0.10% vinegar.

T3: were immersed in a solution containing 0.15% water extract of ginger powder.

T4: were immersed in a solution containing 0.20% aqueous extract of ginger powder.

T5: were immersed in a solution containing 0.25% aqueous extract of ginger powder.

The meat cuts were cut into very small cuts using a knife, minced, and ground in an electric mincer, and prepared for analysis and physical tests.

Physical tests for aged camel meat: Water Holding Capacity (WHC) of meat, Cooking Loss, Drip Loss, and Thawing Loss.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the impact of tenderizing aged camel meat with varying concentrations of aqueous ginger powder extract on its ability to retain water. All aqueous ginger powder extract treatments showed a substantial impact when compared to the positive and negative control treatments. The results for the thigh meat indicate a significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) in treatment T3, treatment T4, and treatment T5, with rates of 28.73%, 28.88%, and 28.56%, compared to the damaging control (T1) and positive control (T2) treatments, which reached rates of 27.66% and 27.89%. For shoulder meat, a significant rise ($P \leq 0.05$) was observed in treatment T4, at a rate of 30.81%, compared to treatment T5, at a rate of 30.32%, this significantly outperformed T2, at a rate of 29.02%, which significantly outperformed T1, at a rate of 28.69%. There were no significant changes between treatments T3 and T4, and between treatments T3 and T5. For back meat, it was observed that treatments T3 and T4 yielded the highest water-holding capacity, at 30.05% and 30.33%, compared to treatment T4, which reached a rate of 29.77%, which significantly outperformed, compared to T2, which reached 28.72%, which significantly outperformed T1, which reached 28.34%.

Table 1. Effect of Tenderizing with Aqueous Extract of Ginger Powder on Water Holding Capacity Aged Camel Meat (means \pm standard error)

Treatments	Meat cuts		
	Thigh	Shoulder	Back
T1	27.66 \pm 1.009 b	28.69 \pm 2.104 d	28.34 \pm 0.851 d
T2	27.89 \pm 2.118 b	29.02 \pm 0.766 c	28.72 \pm 0.927 c
T3	28.73 \pm 0.977 a	30.45 \pm 1.215 ab	30.05 \pm 1.021 a

T4	28.88±1.105 a	30.81±1.044 a	30.33±1.124 a
T5	28.56±2.115 a	30.32±0.862 b	29.77±0.911 b
Sig.	*	*	*

Table 2 shows the effect of tenderizing with different stages of aqueous ginger powder extract on cooking loss in aged camel meat. It is noted that very tenderizing treatments with aqueous ginger powder extract were significantly affected ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to the control treatments in all studied cuts. The results show a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) in treatments T3 and T4, with rates of 34.89 and 34.64%, compared to treatment T5, which averaged 35.76%. This decrease was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to T2, which averaged 36.62%. This decrease was significantly reduced compared to T1, which averaged 37.02%. There were no significant differences between treatments T3 and T4. As for shoulder meat, treatment T4 showed a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) of 35.02% compared to treatment T3, which decreased by 35.39%. This decrease was also significant ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to treatment T5, which decreased by 35.76%. This decrease was also significant ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to T2, which decreased by 37.29%, and this decrease was also significant compared to T1, which decreased by 37.87%. For back loin meat, a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) was observed in treatment T4, at a rate of 34.87%, compared to treatment T3, at a rate of 35.02%, which reduced significantly ($P \leq 0.05$), compared to treatments T2 and T5, at rates of 36.98% and 35.86%, which decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$), likened to T1, which decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table 2. The Effect of Tenderizing with Aqueous Extract of Ginger Powder on Cooking Loss of Old Camel Meat (means \pm standard error)

Treatments	Meat cuts		
	Thigh	Shoulder	Back
T1	37.02±2.248 a	37.87±0.978 a	37.44±2.133 a
T2	36.62±1.457 b	37.29±1.548 b	36.98±1.667 b
T3	34.89±1.875 d	35.39±1.466 d	35.02±0.944 c
T4	34.64±2.089 d	35.02±1.854 e	34.87±2.004 d
T5	35.76±1.885 c	36.19±1.487 c	35.86±1.245 b
Sig.	*	*	*

Table 3 shows the impact of tenderizing aged camel meat with varying concentrations of aqueous ginger powder extract on drip loss. Our study's findings show that, in comparison to the two control treatments, all tenderizing treatments using aqueous ginger powder extract significantly reduced drip loss values ($P \leq 0.05$). It is noted that in camel thigh meat, treatments T3 and T4 decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) by 16.89% and 16.43%, respectively, compared to treatment T5, which decreased significantly (Significantly lower ($P \leq 0.05$) than T1 (18.67%) and significantly lower ($P \leq 0.05$) than T2 (17.93%). Treatments T3 and T4 did not differ significantly from one another. In contrast to treatment T3 (16.52%), treatment T4 demonstrated a substantial decline ($P \leq 0.05$) in shoulder meat at a rate of 16.15%. a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to treatment T5 (17.21%), and a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to T2 (17.49%), which showed a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to T1, which reached a rate of 18.29%. As for the back cut meat, the results of treatment T4 showed a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.05$) at a rate of

16.42% compared to treatment T3 (16.91%), which decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to treatments T2 and T5, which reached a rate of 17.78 and 17.58%, which decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) compared to T1, which reached a rate of 19.02%. There are no significant differences between treatments T2 and T5.

Table 3. The Effect of Tenderizing with Aqueous Extract of Ginger Powder on the Drip Loss of Old Camel Meat (means \pm standard error)

Treatments	Meat cuts		
	Thigh	Shoulder	Back
T1	18.67 \pm 0.248 a	18.29 \pm 0.337 a	19.02 \pm 0.344 a
T2	17.93 \pm 0.197 b	17.46 \pm 0.411 b	17.78 \pm 0.581 b
T3	16.89 \pm 0.584 d	16.52 \pm 0.211 d	16.91 \pm 0.241 c
T4	16.43 \pm 0.554 d	16.15 \pm 0.244 e	16.42 \pm 0.641 d
T5	17.55 \pm 0.248 c	17.21 \pm 0.384 c	17.58 \pm 0.332 b
Sig.	*	*	*

Table 4 shows how thawing loss in aged camel meat is affected by tenderizing it with varying concentrations of aqueous ginger powder extract. In comparison to the negative and positive control treatments, our findings show a significant effect ($P \leq 0.05$) for all aqueous ginger powder extract treatments. Treatment T5 (30.11%) showed a substantial drop ($P \leq 0.05$) in thigh meat, while treatments T3 and T4 showed a significant decline ($P \leq 0.05$) with averages of 29.49% and 29.21% compared to T2 (30.82%), This was substantially lower than T1 (31.49%). Treatments T3 and T4 did not differ significantly from one another. Treatment T4 (average 28.79%) showed a significant ($P \leq 0.05$) decrease in shoulder meat when compared to treatment T3 (29.06%), which in turn decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) when compared to treatment T5 (29.88%), which in turn decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) when compared to T2 (30.64%) and significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) when compared to T1., and that came to 31.15%. In addition, the back piece meat dropped significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) in treatment T4 at a rate of 29.82% when compared to treatment T3 (30.14%), significantly lower ($P \leq 0.05$) when compared to treatment T5 (30.93%), and significantly lower ($P \leq 0.05$) when compared to T2 (31.59%), which achieved a rate of 32.23%.

Table 4. The Effect of Tenderizing with Aqueous Extract of Ginger Powder on Thawing Loss of Old Camel Meat (means \pm standard error)

Treatments	Meat cuts		
	Thigh	Shoulder	Back
T1	31.49 \pm 0.366 a	31.15 \pm 0.663 a	32.23 \pm 0.092 a
T2	30.82 \pm 0.428 b	30.64 \pm 0.318 b	31.59 \pm 0.211 b
T3	29.49 \pm 0.092 d	29.06 \pm 0.415 d	30.14 \pm 0.522 d
T4	29.21 \pm 0.248 d	28.79 \pm 0.552 e	29.82 \pm 0.638 e
T5	30.11 \pm 0.543 c	29.88 \pm 0.344 c	30.93 \pm 0.558 c
Sig.	*	*	*

Conclusion

The results of our study showed that water ginger powder extract significantly increased WHC. A significant decrease was also observed in cooking loss, drip loss, and thawing loss for all studied camel meat cuts—the thigh, shoulder, and back—compared to the two regulator treatments. The best results were obtained when samples were immersed in a solution containing 0.20% aqueous ginger powder (T4). This may be due to ginger containing active compounds that improve camel meat tenderization and affect the body's muscles by stimulating enzymes that break down strong bonds. It also actively breaks the bonds between muscle fiber proteins, increasing their breakdown and dissolution, thus giving them flexibility and suppleness, making them more capable of holding water and reducing cooking loss, drip loss, and thawing loss (Abdeldaiem et al., 2013; He et al., 2015).

References

- Abdeldaiem, M. H., & Hoda, G. M. Ali. (2013). Tenderization of camel meat by using fresh ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) extract. *Food Science & Quality Management*, 21, 12-25.
- Abdelhadi, O. M. A., Babiker, S. A., Hocquette, J. F., Picard, B., Durand, D., & Faye, B. (2019). Effect of ageing on meat quality of the one-humped camel (*Camelus dromedarius*). *Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture*, 25, 150-158.
- Al-Salman, N. T. Sh., & Al-Gharawi, J. K. M. (2019). Effect of Eucalyptus leaves water extract on some productive traits of broilers. *Plant Archives*, 19(Supplement 1), 920-923.
- Baba, W. N., Rasool, N., & Selvamuthukumara, M. (2021). A review on nutritional composition, health benefits, and technological interventions for improving consumer acceptability of camel meat: An ethnic food of the Middle East. *Journal of Ethnic Foods*, 8, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42779-021-00073-2>
- Barbut, S. (2024). Measuring water holding capacity in poultry meat. *Poultry Science*, 103(5), 103577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2023.103577>
- Tan, E. T. T., Ng, J. C., Al Jassim, R., D'Arcy, B. R., Netzel, G., & Fletcher, M. T. (2020). Emerging food safety risk of hepatotoxic indospicine in feral Australian camel meat. *Food Control*, 113, 107205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107205>
- El-Badawi, A. Y., Naggari, S., Abedo, A. A., Hassan, A. A., & Yacout, M. H. (2024). Muscular and edible-organ meat chemical composition, macro- and micro-element distribution and subcutaneous fat properties of camel and beef cattle calves. *Egyptian Journal of Veterinary Science*, 55(5), 1217-1227.
- He, F., Kim, H., Hwang, K., Song, D., Kim, Y., Ham, Y., Kim, S., Yeo, I., Jung, T., & Kim, C. (2015). Effect of ginger extract and citric acid on the tenderness of duck breast muscles. *Korean Journal of Food Science of Animal Resources*, 35(6), 721-730. <https://doi.org/10.5851/kosfa.2015.35.6.721>
- Ibrahim, M. S., Hafez, A. E., El Bayomi, R. M., & Mahmoud, A. F. A. (2025). Review on camel meat: Health benefits, chemical contaminants, health risks, and mitigation strategies. *Egyptian Journal of Veterinary Science*, 56(Special Issue), 515-526.
- Si, R., Wu, D., Na, Q., He, J., Yi, L., Ming, L., Guo, F., & Ji, R. (2022). Effects of various processing methods on the nutritional quality and carcinogenic substances of Bactrian camel (*Camelus bactrianus*) meat. *Foods*, 11(20), 3276. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11203276>
- Suliman, G. M., Al-Owaimer, A. N., Hussein, E. O. S., Abuelfatah, K., & Othman, M. B. (2020). Meat quality characteristics of the Arabian camel (*Camelus dromedarius*) at different ages and post-mortem ageing periods. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences*, 33(8), 1332-1338. <https://doi.org/10.5713/ajas.19.0589>

Tabite, R., Lemrhamed, A., El Abbadi, N., Belhouari, A., Faye, B., & El Khasmi, M. (2019). Relationship between circulating levels of cortisol at slaughter and changes of some parameters of the camel meat during ageing. *Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture*, 31(11), 874-883. <https://doi.org/10.9755/ejfa.2019.v31.i11.2031>

Vashishth, R., Semwal, A. D., Naika, M., Sharma, G. K., & Kumar, R. (2021). Influence of cooking methods on antinutritional factors, oligosaccharides and protein quality of underutilized legume *Macrotyloma uniflorum*. *Food Research International*, 143, 110299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2021.110299>

Younis, M. W. S. Arab, A., Hamad, A., & Sabeq, I. (2025). Assessing the variability in camel and beef meat quality: Implications for consumer acceptance. *Benha Veterinary Medical Journal*, 48, 74-78.

